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ABSTRACT

The impact of high-temperature annealing on the magnetic and microstructural properties of MnFePSi glass-coated microwires is studied. A comparative analysis is conducted to elucidate the influence of annealing conditions (temperature and time) on physical characteristics MnFePSi glass-coated microwires compared to the as-prepared sample. The results reveal a significant influence of the annealing process on MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwires. A notable observation is the increased coercivity (H_c) for the sample annealed at 973 K for 1 h, rising from 761 Oe (as-prepared) to 1200 Oe. However, increasing the annealing time to 2 h leads to a sharp reduction in the coercivity value to 253 Oe. Thermomagnetic curves [field-cooling (FC) and field-heating (FH)] of the annealed samples, measured at both low and high magnetic fields, exhibit perfect matching. This indicates that the relevant contribution of the internal stresses induced by glass coating in the magnetic behavior in both FC and FH protocols. We demonstrate the possibility for tailoring and modification of relevant magnetic phenomena such as metamagnetic phase transition, magnetic behavior, and the control of magnetic response (hardness/softness). These tailored properties pave the way for the exploitation of MnFePSi glass-coated microwire in a wide range of glass-coated microwire applications.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Micro- and nano-magnetic materials capable to undergo thermoelastic martensitic phase transformations (TMPTs) have become an exciting area of research due to their remarkable combination of properties.^{1–7} These materials exhibit a unique synergy of functionalities, offering the potential to revolutionize various technological advancements.^{1–24} Some of the most attractive characteristics include the shape memory (SM) effect, where the material can return to its original form upon application of heat; giant superelasticity (GS), allowing for immense recoverable strain; magnetic field-induced strain (MFIS), enabling control through magnetic fields; and elastocaloric and magnetocaloric (EMC) effects, which present opportunities for efficient solid-state cooling.^{1–26}

Magnetocaloric materials offer a promising solution to mitigate global warming by replacing gas refrigerants.^{22–27} Among these materials, $Gd_5(Si,Ge)_4$ and $La(Fe,Si)_{13}H$ compounds have garnered significant attention due to their large magnetocaloric effect.²⁷ However, their commercialization is hindered by cost competitiveness, attributable to the utilization of rare-earth elements and intricate fabrication processes.^{28,29} Consequently, $(Mn,Fe)_2(P,Si)$ compounds have emerged as attractive alternatives to rare-earth counterparts owing to their substantial magnetocaloric properties and lower cost.^{29,30} Notably, the magnetocaloric properties of these compounds can be tailored to surpass those of rare-earth materials by strategically incorporating additional elements and adjusting compositions.³¹

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The remarkable magnetocaloric properties of $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2(\text{P,Si})$ compounds originate from the presence of a single-phase hexagonal structure, Fe_2P .³² Within this phase, each atom occupies specific preferred sites within the Fe_1P_1 (3f and 2c) and Fe_2P_2 (3g and 1b) layers. Notably, the magnetic moment associated with Fe atoms is significantly higher in the Fe_2 sublattice compared to the Fe_1 sublattice.³² This disparity arises due to metamagnetic ordering within the Fe_1 sublattice, while the Fe_2 sublattice exhibits ferromagnetic interactions. Consequently, during the transition from the paramagnetic to the ferromagnetic phase, a discontinuous change in the magnetic moment of the Fe_1 sublattice is observed. This phenomenon, known as a first-order magnetic phase transition, is accompanied by the magnetoelastic effect.³² The versatility of $(\text{Mn, Fe})_2(\text{P,Si})$ compounds lies in their tunability through the strategic substitution of Fe and P with Mn and Si elements within the Fe_2P hexagonal structure.^{31,33} These substitutions significantly impact the change in lattice parameters, magnetic moments, exchange interactions, and ultimately, the magnetocaloric properties. Notably, a decrease in the lattice parameter “a” leads to the development of antiferromagnetic interactions between each Mn and Fe atom. Conversely, an increase in the lattice parameter “c” leads to a decline in ferromagnetic interactions between Mn and Fe atoms.³⁴ Remarkably, despite significant variations in the lattice parameters, the crystal structure and the characteristic first-order phase transition behavior are maintained due to the magnetoelastic effect. This inherent feature allows $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2(\text{P,Si})$ compounds to achieve large magnetocaloric effects comparable to those exhibited by $\text{Gd}_5(\text{Si, Ge})_4$ and other leading magnetocaloric materials.^{35–37}

The miniaturization trend prevalent in modern technology extends to the field of magnetocaloric devices, further amplifying the appeal of MnFePSi alloys.^{38,39–56} The exceptional characteristic of MnFePSi lies in its ability to be processed into various micro-scale structures, including small particles, wires, ribbons, films, and even intricate bi- and multilayered configurations. The main magnetic parameters such as coercivity, thermomagnetic behavior, magnetic transition, and Curie temperature of MnFePSi alloy are strongly related to many factors such as the chemical compositions, annealing condition, grain size, secondary phases presence, and fabrication-processing techniques.^{54–56} Therefore, a wide variation in Curie temperatures from 100 to 470 K is reported.^{5,11,39–56} Additionally, a relationship between the coercivity, H_c , and grain size consisting in an increase in H_c with decreasing crystallite size was reported.⁵⁵ Typically, H_c -values below 200 Oe were observed.⁵⁵ This remarkable shape versatility translates to a plethora of potential applications.^{38,39–56}

Glass-coated microwires, particularly those with diameters of just a few micrometers, have emerged as a captivating research area due to their diverse applications, especially in sensing technology.^{57–61} Such microwires consist of a metallic nucleus (in the present case of MnFePSi), covered by a thin, insulating and flexible glass shell. This unique morphology offers several advantages. Compared to bulk or thin film samples, MnFePSi microwires provide novel functionalities across various industrial sectors.^{57–61} The glass coating itself provides a threefold benefit: it protects the integrity of the metallic nucleus even under harsh environmental conditions through mechanical protection. Additionally, it acts as an electrical insulator, preventing electrical short circuits within the

device. Finally, the glass coating enhances the corrosion resistance of the microwire, extending its operational lifespan. Furthermore, the thickness of the glass coating can be precisely controlled during the fabrication process, enabling customization to meet specific sensing requirements.

This study presents a comprehensive investigation of the structural and magnetic properties of MnFePSi glass-coated microwires. Notably, the influence of annealing conditions on the magnetostructural properties was explored. The research revealed significant differences in the physical properties of MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwires before and after annealing. A strong variation in the magnetic parameters such as coercivity (175–1200 Oe), magnetic stability, thermomagnetic behavior, thermal stability, and microstructure has observed by changing the annealing condition. These findings highlight the increased sensitivity of MnFePSi microwires to annealing compared to their bulk alloy of the same composition. This sensitivity opens up possibilities for tailoring intriguing physical phenomena, such as metamagnetic phase transitions and bi-stable magnetic behavior.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The following high-purity raw materials are employed: manganese ($\geq 99.5\%$), phosphorus ($\geq 99.5\%$), an iron-phosphorus compound (typically FeP at $\geq 98\%$), and silicon ($\geq 99.999\%$). These materials are meticulously weighed to achieve the desired final nominal composition. Subsequently, the mixture undergoes arc-melting within a strictly controlled argon atmosphere. This melting process results in the formation of an MnFePSi alloy ingot. To compensate for potential minor manganese and phosphorus losses during arc-melting, an excess of 5% (wt. %) of both elements is intentionally added to the initial mixture. At the final step, the Taylor–Ulitsky technique is used to transform the ingot into a microwire.^{58,59} The MnFePSi ingot is heated and melted by a high frequency inductor. At the same time, the surrounding glass is softened. This softened glass is then stretched into a capillary by a rotating bobbin.^{58,59} The molten alloy is drawn into the newly formed glass capillary, forming an MnFePSi core coated by a glass layer. The use of coolant allows to achieve rapid melt quenching during the solidification process. The presence of the insulating glass-coated facilitates the studies of the influence of annealing conditions on the microstructure and magnetic properties of MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwires. For the annealing process, two samples with the same length and the same geometrical parameters are carefully cut from the sample few meter long microwire. Then, each sample was annealed separately. However, to prevent the oxidation during annealing, the tubes the samples were annealed in the tube evacuated and subsequently sealed under an argon atmosphere. The encapsulated samples then underwent annealing at 973 K for durations of 1 and 2 h.

A comprehensive characterization approach was employed to investigate the microstructure, morphology, and elemental composition of MnFePSi glass-coated microwires encompassing both as-cast and annealed states. This analysis utilized a Hitachi TM3000 scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with an energy-dispersive x-ray spectrometer (EDX) to examine the materials at the microscopic level, as described early.^{5,11,38} Additionally,

x-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis using Cu $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) on a BRUKER diffractometer was performed to elucidate the crystal structure of the samples.

Magnetic characterization was conducted using a Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS) across a broad temperature range (5–300 K) and a wide range of magnetic field (up to 90 kOe). This investigation focused on magnetization curves measured parallel to the wire axis to comprehend the magnetic behavior of the MnFePSi microwires annealed at various conditions. To facilitate a more rigorous comparison between bulk and glass-coated microwire samples, the temperature dependence of magnetization (M/M_{5K}) was measured from 5 to 400 K. Here, M represents the magnetization at a specific temperature (T), and M_{5K} denotes the magnetization at 5 K and a magnetic field of 90 kOe. The use of the normalized value (M/M_{5K}) addresses the challenges associated with determining the saturation magnetization of the composite microwires and minimizes potential errors, allowing for a more focused analysis of intrinsic magnetic behavior variations. It is important to note that shape magnetic anisotropy determines the easy magnetization axis, which is aligned with the wire axis in this case. Magnetic fields of up to 90 kOe were applied during characterization. It is further emphasized that all characterizations, including magnetic measurements, XRD analysis, and morphological investigations, were exclusively performed on the glass-coated microwire samples.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. XRD analysis of MnFePSi samples

Figure 1 presents the x-ray diffraction (XRD) data for as-prepared and annealed MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwire at 973 K for different durations 1 and 2 h. The data are collected at room temperature. From the XRD patterns, notable differences have been observed, which reveal the strong effect of the annealing condition on the microstructure behavior of MnFePSi samples. First, all diffractograms display a wide halo at $2\theta \approx 23^\circ$, related to the contribution of amorphous glass coating as reported in our previous works.^{60–65} For the as-prepared sample, three different phases are seen. Meanwhile, two phases are observed in the annealed samples. The main phase reported in all the studied samples is Fe_2P with space group (P-62 m). The secondary phases are hexagonal Mn_5Si_3 ($\text{P}6_3/\text{mcm}$) and cubic Fe_3Si (Fm-3 m) for the as-prepared sample, cubic Fe_3Si (Fm-3 m) for the annealed sample for (1 h), and hexagonal Mn_5Si_3 ($\text{P}6_3/\text{mcm}$) for the sample annealed for 2 h. The absence of the hexagonal Mn_5Si_3 ($\text{P}6_3/\text{mcm}$) phase in the sample annealed for 1 h suggests that Mn atoms occupy the Fe position in the cubic Fe_3Si (Fm-3 m) phase. These observations suggest that the annealing process promotes an increase in the content of the main Fe_2P phase while reducing the secondary phases amount in MnFePSi. For the annealed sample at 973 for 1 h, an enhancement in the signal strength is observed for peaks at 2θ values of 30° , 46.9° , 53.5° , and 65.3° . This indicates a higher content of the main Fe_2P phase (space group P-62 m) in the annealed sample compared to the as-prepared ones. For sample annealed for 2 h, only two peaks are seen at $2\theta = 46.9^\circ$ and 48.3° , which corresponds to the Fe_2P (main phase) and Mn_5Si_3 ($\text{P}6_3/\text{mcm}$) (secondary phase) [see Fig. 1(c)]. The calculation of the

lattice parameter reveals a slight decrease from $a = 0.58 \pm 0.02 \text{ nm}$ for the as-prepared sample to $a = 0.53 \pm 0.02 \text{ nm}$ for the annealed sample for 1 h and then a sharp increase to $0.63 \pm 0.02 \text{ nm}$ for the annealed sample for 2 h [see Fig. 2(a)]. These differences in the microstructure and phase formation significantly affect the magnetic behavior of the annealed samples, which will be discussed in Sec. III B on magnetic property analysis of the magnetic behavior of the annealed. Notably, the analysis of the average grain size (D_g) reveals a significant variation. D_g increases from 36 nm for the as-prepared sample to 133 nm for the annealed sample for 1 h and then reduced to 82 nm for the annealed sample for 2 h [see Fig. 2(b)].

B. Magnetic properties of MnFePSi samples

1. $M(H)$ loop behavior

Figure 3 summarizes the magnetic hysteresis $M(H)$ loops of as-prepared and annealed for different time samples. All magnetic measurement were performed in the in-plan configuration, where the applied magnetic field is parallel to the wire axis. The $M(H)$ loops were measured at a wide range of temperatures, 5–300 K. For the as-prepared sample, the maximum magnetic field of about 90 kOe is used to have the fully saturated sample; meanwhile, 40 kOe is used for the annealed sample. In addition, all magnetic measuring were performed keeping the glass-coated layer. As seen in Fig. 3, a notable change in the magnetic behavior is found between the as-prepared sample and annealed for different time samples. First, the as-prepared sample shows unsaturated loops with a maximum applied magnetic field, i.e., 90 kOe; meanwhile, the saturated magnetic loops are observed in the annealed samples even below 5 kOe. In addition, the hysteresis loops of as-prepared samples show extraordinary meta-magnetic transition for all measuring temperature ranges.^{5,11} Such properties, i.e., extraordinary meta-magnetic transition behavior, do not appear in the annealed loops. In the sample annealed for 1 h, the $M(H)$ loops exhibit normal ferromagnetic behavior, whereas the $M(H)$ loop measured at $T = 300 \text{ K}$ exhibits soft magnetic behavior compared to the $M(H)$ loop measured at $T = 5 \text{ K}$, and the $M(H)$ loop exhibits a harder magnetic behavior.

For the sample annealed for 2 h, the hysteresis loops show magnetically softer character compared to the as-prepared and annealed for 1 h sample. It is worth noting that in the sample annealed for 2 h, the temperature dependence of the magnetic behavior is very weak: there is no significant change in the magnetic behavior with temperature compared to the as-prepared and the annealed for 1 h sample.

For more visual information about the magnetic behavior of as-prepared and annealed for different time MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwire samples, we plotted the dependencies of evolution of H_c and normalized remanence $M_r = M/M_{5K}$ with temperature in Fig. 4. As seen in Fig. 4(a), the $H_c(T)$ dependences show a regular ferromagnetic behavior where H_c increases by decreasing the temperature from 300 to 5 K. The sample annealed for 1 h shows the highest H_c -value compared to the rest of the samples. The maximum H_c -value at 5 K is about 1200 Oe. The sample annealed for 2 h shows the lowest H_c -value: the maximum H_c -value is observed at $T = 5 \text{ K}$, where $H_c \approx 254 \text{ Oe}$. In addition, this sample

FIG. 1. Room temperature x-ray diffraction profile of (a) as-prepared and annealed for (b) 1 and (c) 2 h MnFePSi glass-coated microwires.

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shows only a slight change in magnetic properties with the temperature, where the difference between the lowest and the highest H_c -value is about 65 Oe; meanwhile, the difference between the highest and the lowest coercivity values is 680 and 330 Oe for the annealed for 1 h sample and as-prepared sample, respectively.

As regarding the normalized remanence, the sample annealed for 2 h shows rather weak temperature dependence, where the difference between the highest and the lowest M_r -value is about 0.02. Such thermal stability is not observed in the as-prepared and

annealed for 1 h sample, where the difference between the highest and the lowest M_r -values is 0.3 and 0.18 for as-prepared and annealed for 1 h samples, respectively. In addition, the M_r -value for the annealed for 2 h sample is the highest at all the measuring temperature range compared to the as-prepared and annealed for 1 h sample [see Fig. 4(b)]. This magnetic behavior of the annealed samples must be explained by the sensitivity of the MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwires to the annealing conditions (time and temperature), where a change in temperature causes modification in

FIG. 2. (a) Lattice constant parameter and (b) average grain size of as-prepared and different time annealed MnFePSi glass-coated microwires.

the internal stress originated by the covering glass layer and induces a change in the microstructure of the magnetic metallic nucleus and changing in its magnetic response.

2. ZFC, FC, and FH magnetic curves

Thermomagnetic characterization was conducted by measuring magnetization as a function of temperature (T) under a constant applied magnetic field. The measurements were performed at low magnetic field (50 Oe) (see Fig. 5) and high magnetic field (1 kOe) (Fig. 6), all aligned with the wire axis in the temperature

from 5 to 400 K. A zero-field-cooled (ZFC)--field-heating (FH) protocol was employed to acquire the data. Initially, the sample was cooled down from 400 K in the absence of a magnetic field. Then, a chosen magnetic field was applied, and the magnetization data were collected while heating the sample to 400 K (ZFC curve). Subsequently, without removing the field, the data were collected during cooling [field cooling (FC) curve] followed by heating again (FH curve). A constant heating/cooling rate of 2 K/min was maintained throughout the measurements.

For as-prepared samples, all curves show negative M(em) values due to the high coercivity value, where $H_c \approx 467$ to 761 Oe

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FIG. 3. The in-plane hysteresis loops of (a) as-prepared and annealed at 973 K for (b) 1 and (c) 2 h MnFePSi glass-coated microwires measured at different temperature range 300–5 K.

FIG. 4. (a) Coercivity, H_c , and (b) remanence ($M_r = M/M_{5k}$) temperature dependence of as-prepared and annealed MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwires.

for $M(H)$ loops measured at temperature range 5–300 K, as previously reported by us.^{5,11} For ZFC curves measured at low magnetic field, significant changing is observed for as-prepared and annealed samples. In the as-prepared sample, the ZFC shows a regular ferromagnetic behavior, where the magnetization increases monotonically with decreasing the temperature up to 5 K, where the maximum value is obtained. For the sample annealed for 1 and 2 h, the ZFC curves show irreversible magnetic behavior below $T = 150$ K. This irreversibility can be due to different phases and the enhancement in antiferromagnetic ordering contribution at low temperature. For FC and FH curves, both as-prepared and annealed for 1 h samples show similar temperature dependencies, where FC and FH curves have a monotonic increasing by decreasing the temperature from 400 to 5 K. In addition, both (FC and FH) curves present similar behavior in a wide range of measuring temperatures. This can indicate that the glass covering layer of the MnFePSi metallic alloy does not affect low field behavior of the FC and FH curves. The FC and FH curves for the sample annealed for 2 h show the same behavior, with both (FC and FH) curves being close to each other and having the same response with temperature upon a constant applied magnetic field. All FC, FH, and ZFC curves show a strong change in their behavior with temperature with irreversible magnetic behavior observed at $T = 150$ K. By increasing the applied magnetic field to 1 kOe, FC and FH curves show completely different behavior for the as-prepared sample, where the FC curve shows large irreversible magnetic behavior at $T = 80$ K. Meanwhile, the FC and FH curves for the annealed samples show behavior similar to that observed upon a low applied magnetic field. Thus, the annealing improves the stability of ZFC, FC, and FH behavior at a wide range of temperatures and magnetic fields.

The observed change in XRD must be related to the recrystallization process of the as-prepared sample during annealing. Such recrystallization must be strongly correlated with changes in magnetic properties.⁶⁶ The s-prepared sample is characterized by a small average grain size, D_g (about 20 nm), while a substantial

increase in D_g (up to 100 nm) is observed upon annealing. Nanocrystalline materials, with randomly dispersed nanocrystalline grains, exemplify this correlation and often exhibit improved magnetic softness.⁶⁶ This improved softness can be attributed to the relationship between the average crystalline grain size (D_g) and the exchange correlation length (L). When L significantly exceeds D_g ($L \gg D_g$), an averaging-out of macroscopic magnetic anisotropy occurs, leading to enhanced magnetic softness.^{67,68} However, the process of recrystallization is characterized by an increase in the crystalline phase content and the average crystalline grain size (D_g). Typically, such changes are associated with magnetic hardening of these materials.^{67,68} However, nano-sized grains obtained in rapidly quenched materials may have an unstable structure. Therefore, the dissolution of such nanocrystallites, nucleation, and growth of more stable nanocrystals is predicted in such materials.⁶⁹ Such grain size refinement in glass-coated microwires with nanocrystalline structure was previously experimentally observed and was explained in terms of nucleation and growth of new, more stable nanocrystals, rather than the growth of existing nanocrystals inherited from the rapid melt quenching.⁷⁰ Such grain refinement is observed Fig. 2(b) (2 h annealing). Notably, in the context of glass-coated microwires, devitrified microwires can initially retain rectangular hysteresis loops during the early stages of devitrification. However, as the crystallization process progresses, magnetic hardening often becomes increasingly evident.^{63–65}

The observed temperature dependence of magnetic properties (H_c , M_r , ZFC, FC, and FH) aligns with the established correlation between microstructures and magnetic properties in annealed samples.^{63–68} Furthermore, the modest variation in magnetic properties of the annealed samples is likely attributable to the influence of internal stress on the micromagnetic structure. Further investigation into the micromagnetic structure of the post-annealed MnFePSi samples is necessary to gain deeper insights. Our findings suggest that annealing at 973 K for 1 or 2 h induces recrystallization, atomic ordering, and a reduction in internal stresses within

FIG. 5. ZFC, FC, and FH temperature dependence of (a) as-prepared and annealed for (b) 1 and (c) 2 h MnFePSi glass-coated microwire measured at a low magnetic field ($H = 50$ Oe).

the microwires. Additionally, the differences magnetic behavior observed in the annealed MnFePSi glass-coated microwires can be potentially explained by the emergence of two distinct magnetic phases with contrasting magnetic anisotropies.

FIG. 6. FC and FH temperature dependence of (a) as-prepared and annealed for (b) 1 and (c) 2 h MnFePSi glass-coated microwire measured at a high magnetic field ($H = 1$ kOe).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we observed that high-temperature annealing at 973 K for varying durations (1 and 2 h) significantly impacts the magnetic and microstructural properties of as-prepared MnFePSi

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glass-coated microwires. Annealing reduces the presence of secondary phases observed in the as-prepared sample, while enhancing the dominant Fe_2P phase responsible for the material's thermal magnetic response. Notably, the hysteresis loops reveal that annealing suppresses the metamagnetic phase transition observed in the as-prepared sample and promotes ferromagnetic ordering. This results in homogenous behavior with a low saturation field of less than 5 kOe, compared to 90 kOe for the as-prepared sample. Additionally, the sample annealed at 973 K for 1 h exhibits the highest coercivity value, reaching nearly 1.2 kOe. Interestingly, the sample annealed for 2 h demonstrates unique thermal stability, with its remanent magnetization (M_r) remaining stable across a wide temperature range (5–300 K). This study highlights the potential of annealing to tailor magnetic properties in MnFePSi glass-coated microwires, paving the way for applications in glass-coated microwire technology that exploit these tailored properties.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Mohamed Salaheldeen: Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Valentina Zhukova:** Data curation (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal). **Arcady Zhukov:** Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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